

Title: Blockchain Architect and Fintech Entrepreneur

Name: Diogo Romano Souza

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INTRODUCTION:

Visionary and Blockchain Mastermind in South America whose goal is to create new technologies in electronic payment market, to bring more creative and simple solutions to the users having security as top priority. PagChain is the most sophisticated platform of Blockchain As a Service (BAAS) in the market.

AIM:

To revolutionize the Fintech world bringing a disruptive and innovative solution using the Blockchain in various types of business.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

A laboratory study was designed and put into practice inside of one of the biggest banks in Brazil in order to test a disruptive method in the use of Blockchain as a service. Different groups of different activities exhaustively worked together to put in the market a platform that revolutionizes the security and efficiency of deals based in tokens (smart contracts) and crypto currencies.

RESULTS:

The result came with 3 different startups and dozens of use cases in enterprises that ranges from Fintechs to Insurance and Energy Companies.

CONCLUSIONS:

According to the results of this study, a huge and solid platform was released to the market in order to revolutionize the relationship of the clients and the companies.

KEYWORDS:

Blockchain, crypto currency, bitcoin, smart contracts, Money revolution

BIOGRAPHY:

Diogo Romano is a 35 years-old and a Post Graduated Developer that created the US\$ 100 billion money transaction company in Brazil REDECARD acquired by a huge Brazilian Bank. Diogo has left the company and dedicated his efforts to the disruptive world of the crypto currency. Convinced that the future is about to face a Bank Disruption Diogo has already created three companies using Blockchain Technology. Winner of Fintech Prizes in Brazil as INOVABRA and ESTACIO ASTRONAUT he is CEO of Pagchain a São Paulo located Blockchain Company.